

Human rights violations in the criminal justice system of Pakistan: wrongful convictions, torture, and unfair trials

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ABSTRACT: This article digs into the problems in Pakistan's justice system, showing how real people are affected. In a country where justice should be solid, things like wrongful convictions, torture, and unfair trials have hurt individuals and society as a whole. These aren't just legal mistakes; they're stories of people's lives falling apart, bringing a lot of pain to them and their families. The dark cloud of torture and abuse during custody is a big issue, emphasizing the need for transparency and accountability. Unfair trials, where people don't get proper legal help and face long waits before trial, go against the core ideas of justice. Thankfully, groups in Pakistan are working hard to make things better, but there are still challenges in getting government plans to work well. Looking from an international viewpoint, organizations like the United Nations are crucial in pushing for human rights in Pakistan. To sum it up, it's really important to tackle these issues. We need solid changes in the laws, careful oversight, and strong support from the international community to build a justice system that truly follows the principles of fairness and respect for everyone.

Keywords: Wrongful Convictions, Torture, Unfair Trails, Justice System, HRCP.

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1. Introduction

The criminal justice system serves as a cornerstone of any society, acting as the vanguard for safeguarding individual liberties, protecting the innocent, and ensuring that the guilty face justice. In Pakistan, a nation with a rich and complex tapestry of cultures and traditions, the criminal justice system plays a pivotal role in maintaining law and order. However, the effective functioning of this system relies fundamentally on upholding the principles of human rights.

Human rights form the bedrock of a just and equitable society. They are not merely an aspiration but a legal and moral obligation that binds the state, its institutions, and its agents. In the context of Pakistan, where a diverse population seeks justice and security, the protection and preservation of human rights are paramount. This article seeks to shed light on the challenges and injustices that persist within Pakistan's criminal justice system, with a particular focus on wrongful convictions, torture, and unfair trials (Bibi, S.,2022).

The criminal justice system in Pakistan, like in many countries, consists of an intricate web of legal and law enforcement mechanisms. It comprises police, lawyers, judges, prisons, and a labyrinth of rules and regulations. While these components are designed to ensure public safety and administer justice, they are not immune to the fallibility that can lead to severe human rights abuses. The protection of individual rights, including the right to a fair trial, the prohibition of torture, and the presumption of innocence, is indispensable to fostering a just society (Qayum, S.,2016).

Wrongful convictions, a harrowing ordeal for those who experience them, are a stark reminder of the system's vulnerability to error. In the pursuit of justice, miscarriages often occur, resulting in the imprisonment of innocent individuals. The consequences are not only felt by the wrongfully convicted but also by their families, who endure anguish and grief. It is vital to examine the factors contributing to wrongful convictions and identify the shortcomings in the legal process that allow such injustices to persist.

Torture, a gross violation of human rights, is a stain on any society's conscience. Despite international treaties and conventions prohibiting its use, instances of torture persist within Pakistan's criminal justice system. These violations not only lead to physical and psychological suffering but also undermine the legitimacy of the system itself. This article will delve into documented cases of torture and explore the ethical and legal implications of this practice (Qayyum, S. A.,2023).

Furthermore, the specter of unfair trials looms large over the criminal justice system in Pakistan. Denial of legal representation, lengthy pretrial detentions, and military courts for civilians are issues that challenge the system's commitment to due process and the right to a fair trial. Such trials not only endanger individual rights but also erode public trust in the legal system.

As we go into the depths of these critical issues, it is crucial to recognize that they are not insurmountable challenges but rather areas where reform, accountability, and commitment to human rights can lead to meaningful change. By shedding light on wrongful convictions, torture, and unfair trials, we can contribute to a broader conversation on how Pakistan's criminal justice system can better uphold human rights and truly serve justice for all its citizens.

2. Wrongful convictions

In the intricate tapestry of Pakistan's criminal justice system, wrongful convictions represent a somber facet that has marred the lives of countless individuals and cast a shadow over the pursuit of justice. These tragic errors of justice have left a deep impact not only on those wrongfully convicted but also on their families, who bear the heavy burden of anguish, despair, and the irreplaceable loss of precious years (Bibi, S.,2022). This section provides a broader exploration of wrongful convictions in Pakistan, shedding light on the profound impact on individuals and families and delving into the root causes behind these grave miscarriages of justice.

Shattered Lives and Lost Years: The Profound Toll of Wrongful Convictions

The human cost of wrongful convictions in Pakistan is immeasurable, extending well beyond the confines of prison walls. The stories of individuals such as Iqbal, who spent over a decade behind bars for a crime he did not commit, and Sadia, whose dreams and

aspirations were unjustly derailed by an erroneous verdict, offer poignant illustrations of the human toll. Iqbal, separated from his family and children, yearned for his father's embrace, while Sadia, her reputation tarnished and opportunities vanquished, grappled with the enduring consequences of an unjust conviction.

However, the impact of wrongful convictions extends beyond the wrongfully convicted individuals themselves. Families, including parents, spouses, and children, experience profound emotional trauma as they witness their loved ones suffer injustice. Additionally, socioeconomic hardships often accompany a family member's imprisonment, exacerbating the already severe burdens they carry. Wrongful convictions are not just legal errors; they are profound human tragedies that reverberate throughout society (Qayum, S.,2016).

Root Causes of Wrongful Convictions

Wrongful convictions in Pakistan often result from a convergence of systemic deficiencies and individual injustices, each contributing to this tragic phenomenon:

- Inadequate police investigations, the mishandling of evidence, and the misuse of crucial information can lead to wrongful convictions. In some instances, shortcuts taken during investigations can result in the arrest and imprisonment of innocent individuals.
- Coerced or forced confessions, often extracted under duress or through the use of torture, play a significant role in wrongful convictions. These confessions, though inadmissible in court, continue to plague the criminal justice system.
- A lack of effective legal representation, particularly for marginalized individuals or those unable to afford legal services, is a significant contributing factor to wrongful convictions. Many accused individuals lack access to competent counsel who can safeguard their rights during legal proceedings.
- An overburdened and under-resourced judicial system can lead to rushed trials, insufficient scrutiny of evidence, and hasty dispensation of justice, all of which elevate the risk of wrongful convictions.

These factors underscore the urgent need for comprehensive reform within Pakistan's criminal justice system. Addressing wrongful convictions necessitates a multifaceted approach that encompasses improvements in investigative procedures, the protection of detainees' rights, enhanced legal representation, and a heightened awareness of the profound human consequences of wrongful convictions (Khan, I. A.,2022). By casting a broader spotlight on specific cases and the systemic issues they reveal, we can take the initial steps toward building a more just and equitable legal system in Pakistan.

3. Torture and Custodial Abuse

Within Pakistan's criminal justice system, the specter of torture and custodial abuse casts a long and sinister shadow, raising serious questions about the treatment of individuals in custody and the ethical standards that underpin justice. In this section, we examine the use of torture and custodial abuse in Pakistan, drawing attention to documented cases that highlight the gravity of the issue. We also delve into the legal and ethical implications of torture, underlining its explicit prohibition under international human rights law (Qayyum, S. A.,2023).

Torture and Custodial Abuse: A Disturbing Reality

Torture and custodial abuse in the Pakistani criminal justice system are stark and unsettling realities, inflicting unimaginable physical and psychological suffering on detainees and prisoners. The dark and hidden corners of police stations and detention centers have,

regrettably, witnessed the use of coercive tactics, brutal force, and violence as methods of investigation and control (Islam, S.,2022).

Examples of documented cases paint a distressing picture of the extent of the problem. Instances of severe beatings, electroshocks, stress positions, sexual abuse, and threats to individuals in custody have been reported, perpetuating a culture of fear and impunity. One such case involved an individual who, while in police custody, suffered life-altering injuries due to brutal torture, an ordeal that tragically underscored the depths of the issue.

The Legal and Ethical Implications of Torture

Torture is a grave violation of human rights, one that is explicitly prohibited under international human rights law, including the United Nations Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman, or Degrading Treatment or Punishment. Pakistan, as a signatory to this convention, has a clear obligation to prohibit and prevent torture within its jurisdiction (Gondal, 2017).

The ethical implications of torture are equally severe. Torture is an affront to human dignity, a breach of the principle of the inherent worth of every human being. It undermines the trust citizen's place in the criminal justice system, corrodes public confidence in the rule of law, and perpetuates a cycle of violence and abuse.

Moreover, the use of coerced confessions obtained through torture undermines the credibility and integrity of legal proceedings. Innocent individuals may be wrongly convicted based on unreliable and involuntary statements, further entrenching the problem of wrongful convictions.

As the world continues to move toward a greater respect for human rights and the rule of law, Pakistan's commitment to ending torture and custodial abuse is pivotal. Addressing this issue requires comprehensive reforms, including strengthening the mechanisms for the oversight of detention centers, ensuring the prompt investigation of allegations of abuse, and implementing strict accountability measures for perpetrators.

By confronting the documented cases of torture and custodial abuse, we not only acknowledge the gravity of the problem but also emphasize the imperative of adhering to legal and ethical standards that uphold the dignity and rights of every individual, regardless of their circumstances. In doing so, we strive to bring about a criminal justice system that truly embodies the principles of justice, fairness, and respect for human rights.

4. Unfair Trials and Lack of Due Process

The right to a fair trial and due process are not just lofty ideals; they are the cornerstones of any just and equitable legal system. However, within Pakistan's criminal justice system, instances of unfair trials have cast a troubling shadow on the pursuit of justice. This section delves into the issues surrounding unfair trials in Pakistan, with a specific focus on the denial of legal representation, lengthy pretrial detentions, and the use of military courts for civilians. Furthermore, we emphasize the profound significance of due process rights and the grievous impact of their violation on the accused (Hafeezullah Ishaq,2014).

Unfair Trials: The Denial of Legal Representation

One of the most troubling aspects of unfair trials in Pakistan is the denial of legal representation, a fundamental right enshrined in international human rights law. Individuals accused of crimes, particularly those who lack the means to secure legal counsel, often find themselves navigating the complex legal terrain alone, without the benefit of a trained attorney to safeguard their rights.

These individuals face significant disadvantages, struggling to understand the legal proceedings and often unable to present a robust defense. In many cases, they are left at the mercy of the prosecution, exacerbating the risk of wrongful convictions and the erosion of trust in the justice system. The denial of legal representation does not merely impede the accused's ability to defend themselves; it undermines the integrity and credibility of the entire legal process (Korai, A.G, 2018).

Lengthy Pretrial Detentions: A Grave Injustice

Another issue central to unfair trials in Pakistan is the phenomenon of lengthy pretrial detentions. Accused individuals may languish in custody for months, or even years, without their cases being heard. This not only infringes upon their right to a speedy trial but also presents a host of hardships, including separation from families, loss of employment, and psychological stress.

The prolonged pretrial detention of individuals, particularly when their cases are eventually dismissed or result in acquittal, represents a grave injustice (Hussain, T.2018). It not only negates the presumption of innocence, a fundamental tenet of due process, but also inflicts severe harm on the accused and their families, who must endure the brunt of the consequences of a system marred by inefficiency and delay.

Military Courts for Civilians: A Disturbing Departure from Due Process

The use of military courts to try civilians is yet another facet of unfair trials in Pakistan. These courts operate outside the purview of civilian jurisdiction, raising serious concerns about the protection of due process rights and the right to a fair trial. The military court system is often criticized for its lack of transparency, inadequate legal safeguards, and the potential for coerced confessions (Wahla,M.N. 2019). This practice not only infringes upon the principle of civilian control over the military but also compromises the fundamental right to a fair trial before an impartial tribunal. The accused in military courts for civilians often lack the same protections and rights afforded to them in the civilian judicial system, undermining the very essence of due process.

The Profound Significance of Due Process Rights

Due process rights are not just legal formalities; they are the bedrock of justice, essential for ensuring that individuals are treated fairly and with dignity. The violation of these rights not only damages the prospects of the accused but also tarnishes the principles of justice and fairness that underpin any legal system.

The denial of legal representation, prolonged pretrial detentions, and the use of military courts for civilians contribute to the erosion of these foundational rights, perpetuating a culture of unfairness and injustice. By shedding light on these issues, we underscore the urgency of comprehensive legal reforms aimed at upholding due process and fair trial rights for all individuals within Pakistan's criminal justice system (Munir, A. I.2023).

In addressing these concerns, we take a vital step toward a legal system that reflects the principles of justice, fairness, and the unwavering commitment to the rights of the accused, regardless of their circumstances.

5. Role of Legal and Human Rights Organizations

Legal and human rights organizations play a pivotal role in Pakistan in documenting human rights violations, advocating for justice, and pushing for critical legal reforms. Their dedication to upholding human rights and promoting a just legal system is paramount. In this section, we explore the efforts of these organizations and provide examples of cases where they have been instrumental in challenging wrongful convictions and advocating for much-needed reforms.

Documenting Human Rights Violations

Legal and human rights organizations in Pakistan are tireless in their efforts to document and record human rights violations. They serve as watchdogs, meticulously cataloging instances of torture, unfair trials, wrongful convictions, and other forms of abuse within the criminal justice system. Their work provides a vital record of these violations, often in the face of significant challenges, such as threats to their safety and security.

Advocating for Justice

These organizations serve as vocal advocates for justice, championing the cause of those who have suffered human rights abuses. They seek to ensure that the stories of victims are heard, their grievances addressed, and their rights upheld. Legal and human rights organizations provide legal representation, counseling, and support to victims and their families, as well as pursuing legal action to challenge injustices.

6. Legal and Human Rights Organizations Making a Difference

The Asma Jahangir Legal Aid Cell:

Named in honor of the renowned human rights advocate Asma Jahangir, this organization has been instrumental in challenging wrongful convictions by the name of AGHS legal aid cell. They have taken on cases of individuals wrongfully convicted and worked diligently to secure their release. Their dedication to justice has led to the exoneration of individuals who had languished in prison for years (AGHS, 1983).

Justice Project Pakistan:

This organization focuses on criminal justice reform and the protection of prisoners' rights. They have been pivotal in challenging prolonged pretrial detentions, advocating for the rights of prisoners, and addressing systemic issues that contribute to unfair trials (Justice Project Pakistan JPP, 2016).

The Human Rights Commission of Pakistan (HRCP)

HRCP plays a multifaceted role, documenting human rights violations and advocating for reform. They have consistently called attention to cases of torture and custodial abuse and have pressed for meaningful changes within the criminal justice system (HRCP, 1987).

Aurat Foundation:

Focused on women's rights, the Aurat Foundation has played a critical role in raising awareness of gender-based violence within the criminal justice system. They have advocated for reforms to protect the rights of women who have been victims of abuse (Aurat Foundation, 1986).

The Center for Social Justice:

The Center for Social Justice is an organization based in United Kingdom. This organization focuses on issues of social justice and human rights, working to ensure that the rights of marginalized communities are upheld within the criminal justice system. They have played a key role in advocating for due process rights for all individuals, regardless of their background (CSJ, 2004).

Advocating for Reforms and Legal Change

Legal and human rights organizations also channel their efforts into advocating for broader legal reforms. They work with lawmakers, government agencies, and other

stakeholders to press for changes that address the systemic issues contributing to human rights violations. Their influence has been instrumental in pushing for legislative and policy reforms aimed at creating a more just and equitable legal system.

In confronting the grave human rights violations within Pakistan's criminal justice system, legal and human rights organizations serve as champions of justice, pushing for systemic changes, advocating for victims, and tirelessly documenting instances of abuse. Their work is not only a testament to their commitment to human rights but also a critical force for positive change within Pakistan's legal landscape. By supporting their efforts and acknowledging their contributions, we take significant steps toward a more just and equitable society for all.

Government Initiatives and Reforms

Within Pakistan, there have been government initiatives and reforms aimed at addressing human rights violations within the criminal justice system. These initiatives reflect a recognition of the need for change and a commitment to upholding human rights. In this section, we examine some of these efforts and analyze their effectiveness, while also considering the challenges in implementing them (Zullah, M. A.1992).

7. Efforts to Address Human Rights Violations

The National Commission for Human Rights (NCHR):

Established in 2012 in Pakistan through the Act XVI of 2012, NCHR is an independent institution responsible for promoting and protecting human rights in Pakistan. It plays a vital role in investigating and addressing human rights violations within the criminal justice system. NCHR's efforts have included the investigation of custodial deaths, torture cases, and monitoring prison conditions.(NCHR, 2012)

Reform of the Anti-Terrorism Courts:

The government has initiated reforms to enhance the fairness and transparency of anti-terrorism courts. These courts have often faced criticism for their swift trials and potential due process violations (Imran, 2020). The aim is to align these courts more closely with international human rights standards.

Prison Reforms:

Efforts have been made to reform the prison system in Pakistan, addressing issues related to overcrowding, inadequate healthcare, and inhumane conditions. These reforms seek to improve the rights and living conditions of prisoners, particularly those who are pretrial detainees.

Mandatory Video Recording of Interrogations:

To address issues related to coerced confessions and custodial abuse, there have been proposals to introduce mandatory video recording of interrogations. This measure aims to enhance transparency and accountability within the criminal justice system.

Challenges in Implementation

Despite these initiatives, challenges persist in implementing effective reforms to combat human rights violations within Pakistan's criminal justice system:

- A lack of financial and human resources poses a significant challenge to the effective implementation of reforms. The criminal justice system is often under-resourced, and initiatives require investment in infrastructure, personnel, and training.

- Resistance to change within various institutions, including the police and judiciary, can hinder the successful implementation of reforms. Cultural and institutional norms may present obstacles to reform efforts.
- The commitment of political leaders and policymakers to prioritizing human rights and reforms is crucial. The effectiveness of reforms depends on sustained political will and support.
- Pakistan's legal framework is complex, with various overlapping laws and regulations. Harmonizing these laws to ensure they align with international human rights standards can be a challenging and time-consuming process.
- Ensuring that reforms are enforced and that there is accountability for violations is an ongoing challenge. It requires effective oversight mechanisms and the commitment of law enforcement agencies to uphold the law.
- Public awareness about human rights and the importance of reforms is vital. Advocacy and education efforts are essential to engage the public in supporting these initiatives (Muneer, S.2017).

The Road Ahead

Addressing human rights violations within Pakistan's criminal justice system is a complex and ongoing process. While government initiatives demonstrate a commitment to change, the challenges in implementing reforms should not be underestimated. Sustained efforts, political will, public support, and collaboration with civil society and international organizations are all vital components of this endeavor.

It is imperative that Pakistan continues to work towards a legal system that is just, transparent, and in full compliance with international human rights standards. By confronting these challenges head-on and learning from both successes and setbacks, Pakistan can make meaningful progress in ensuring human rights are respected and protected within its criminal justice system.

International Perspectives and Accountability

International human rights bodies and organizations play a critical role in monitoring, addressing, and advocating for the protection of human rights in Pakistan. Their involvement serves as an essential mechanism for holding perpetrators of human rights violations accountable and for promoting justice and respect for human rights. In this section, we explore the role of international entities in addressing human rights issues in Pakistan and examine potential avenues for accountability at the international level.

8. The Role of International Human Rights Bodies and Organizations

United Nations Human Rights Council (UNHRC):

The UNHRC is a primary international body that monitors and addresses human rights violations worldwide. Pakistan is a member of the UNHRC, and the council conducts periodic reviews of its human rights record. The UNHRC engages with the Pakistani government on issues such as torture, freedom of expression, and minority rights (UNHCR, 1950).

United Nations Special Procedures:

Various special procedures, such as Special Rapporteurs and Independent Experts, are appointed by the UNHRC to examine specific human rights issues in Pakistan. They conduct fact-finding missions, report on their findings, and make recommendations for addressing human rights violations.

International Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs):

Organizations like Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch have a significant presence in Pakistan and closely monitor human rights violations. They provide reports and conduct advocacy campaigns to raise international awareness and pressure governments to address human rights concerns.

The International Criminal Court (ICC):

While Pakistan is not a party to the ICC, the court has jurisdiction over certain crimes that have occurred on the territory of non-member states, particularly if the UN Security Council refers cases. The ICC could potentially investigate and prosecute individuals responsible for severe human rights violations (ICC July 1, 2002).

9. Potential Avenues for Accountability at the International Level**United Nations Fact-Finding Missions:**

The United Nations can initiate fact-finding missions to investigate specific human rights abuses. These missions can document evidence of violations and bring them to the international community's attention.

Universal Jurisdiction:

Some countries exercise universal jurisdiction, allowing them to prosecute individuals for grave human rights violations, regardless of where the crimes occurred. Perpetrators of such crimes may be arrested and tried when traveling to countries with universal jurisdiction laws.

Individual Communications to Treaty Bodies:

Victims of human rights abuses can submit individual communications to treaty bodies, such as the Human Rights Committee or the Committee against Torture. These committees can consider individual complaints and recommend remedies.

International Pressure and Sanctions:

The international community, including the United Nations and regional organizations, can impose sanctions, travel bans, or arms embargoes on individuals or entities responsible for human rights abuses in Pakistan.

International Media and Advocacy:

International media outlets and advocacy campaigns can raise awareness of human rights violations in Pakistan, leading to public pressure and international condemnation. This can influence governments and institutions to take action.

Support for Local Civil Society:

International organizations and governments can provide support to local civil society organizations in Pakistan, enabling them to document human rights abuses and advocate for reform.

10. Challenges in Accountability

While international mechanisms exist to address human rights violations, there are several challenges in holding perpetrators accountable at the international level:

- Pakistan, like many countries, may raise concerns about sovereignty and resist international intervention in domestic matters.

- International bodies often lack enforcement mechanisms, making it challenging to ensure that their recommendations are carried out.
- Geopolitical considerations can influence international responses to human rights issues. Strategic alliances and diplomatic relations may hinder stronger actions against human rights violators.
- The legal processes for international accountability can be lengthy and complicated, requiring cooperation and adherence from multiple actors.
- International bodies and organizations may have limited resources and capacity to address the full scope of human rights violations in Pakistan (Rashid,A. 2020).

The Road Ahead

International perspectives and accountability mechanisms are essential components of addressing human rights violations in Pakistan. While challenges exist, the international community's scrutiny and advocacy can contribute to fostering a climate of accountability and justice, as well as encouraging domestic reforms that promote respect for human rights. Collaborative efforts between international and local actors remain crucial in the pursuit of a more just and equitable society in Pakistan.

11. Recommendations and Conclusion

In order to address the pressing human rights issues within Pakistan's criminal justice system, it is imperative that a multifaceted approach be adopted. First and foremost, comprehensive legal and procedural reforms are essential to ensure that the system aligns with international human rights standards. This includes improving investigative procedures, enhancing the protection of detainees' rights, and ensuring access to effective legal representation for all accused individuals. Furthermore, the eradication of torture and custodial abuse demands stringent oversight mechanisms, training for law enforcement agencies, and the implementation of mandatory video recording of interrogations to enhance transparency and accountability. Addressing wrongful convictions necessitates the establishment of innocence projects and a thorough review of case files, while unfair trials can be mitigated through reforms that promote the right to a fair trial, including reducing pretrial detentions and discontinuing the use of military courts for civilians. Moreover, the government must commit to sustaining these reforms and allocate adequate resources to ensure their effective implementation. International organizations and the global community should continue to pressure for accountability and justice, and the engagement of local civil society is critical in advocating for human rights. By pursuing these recommendations collectively, Pakistan can make meaningful progress toward a more just, equitable, and rights-respecting criminal justice system.

In Pakistan, the criminal justice system serves as the guardian of justice and order, but it is a system plagued by serious human rights violations. This article has explored the profound and urgent issues within Pakistan's criminal justice system, with a specific focus on wrongful convictions, torture, and unfair trials. These issues are not just legal or ethical concerns; they are fundamental questions of human dignity and justice.

Wrongful convictions have shattered countless lives, leaving innocent individuals to endure the horrors of imprisonment for crimes they did not commit. These injustices are not isolated errors; they are a testament to systemic flaws in the investigation and legal process. The toll is immeasurable, affecting not only the wrongfully convicted but also their families who bear the weight of anguish, despair, and lost years.

Torture and custodial abuse cast a dark shadow over Pakistan's criminal justice system. The use of coercion, brutality, and violence as tools of investigation are inexcusable violations of human rights. Documented cases illustrate the devastating

consequences of torture, not only for the victims but also for the credibility and integrity of the entire system.

Unfair trials, marked by the denial of legal representation, prolonged pretrial detentions, and the use of military courts for civilians, pose a direct challenge to the principles of justice and due process. These practices not only endanger individual rights but also erode public trust in the legal system.

Legal and human rights organizations in Pakistan have been at the forefront of documenting human rights violations, advocating for justice, and supporting the victims of abuse. Their efforts have been pivotal in challenging wrongful convictions, advocating for reform, and raising international awareness about human rights issues in Pakistan.

While there have been government initiatives to address human rights violations, the challenges in implementation remain significant. Comprehensive reforms are vital to ensuring that Pakistan's legal system aligns with international human rights standards. Progress in this direction is not only a legal imperative but also a moral obligation.

The international community, including organizations and bodies like the United Nations, plays a vital role in monitoring and addressing human rights issues in Pakistan. These entities are essential in advocating for justice and accountability. They provide crucial oversight and pressure for reform, raising the profile of human rights violations on the global stage.

In conclusion, the urgent need for addressing wrongful convictions, torture, and unfair trials within Pakistan's criminal justice system cannot be overstated. These issues have real and profound consequences for individuals and society as a whole. As conscientious global citizens, it is our responsibility to stay informed about human rights issues, support advocacy efforts, and promote reforms within the criminal justice system. By working together, we can contribute to a more just and equitable society, where the principles of justice, fairness, and respect for human rights are upheld for all.

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